

Role of Indigenous Practices and Local Communities In Effective Conservation

Qaisur Rahman and D N Sadhu

University Department of Zoology, Vinoba Bhave University, Jharkhand
Corresponding E-mail : qaisur.rahman@gmail.com

Plans to greatly expand the conserved area of land and sea threaten to harm already marginalized people and may fail to effectively conserve nature. There is increasing understanding of what types and qualities of work for people and for biodiversity in the face of complex social ecological and institutional dynamics and growing evidence. This is crucial in the current debate among conservation policy makers regarding how to effectively conserve biodiversity at the same time as supporting the well-being and rights for instance in the negotiation and subsequent implementation of the CBD (2030) goals and targets. Integrating social dimensions to conservation science requires considering not only the economic impacts on communities but also efforts to elicit a broader understanding of well-being and potential harms from among the range of interrelated social cultural economic environmental and political values experiences its causes and impacts. To address this knowledge gap a review of the social and ecological outcomes arising from different forms of conservation governance and identified common pathways through which occur. Only studies that empirically evidenced both social and ecological outcomes and links between them were included in the analysis. The findings suggest that equitable conservation which empowers and supports the environmental stewardship of Indigenous peoples and local communities represents the primary pathway to effective long-term conservation of biodiversity particularly when upheld in wider law and policy. Whether for protected areas in biodiversity hotspots or restoration of highly modified ecosystems whether involving highly traditional or diverse and dynamic local communities conservation can become more effective through an increased focus on governance type and quality and fostering solutions that reinforce the role capacity and rights of Indigenous peoples and local communities.

Keywords: Role, Indigenous Practices, Local Communities, Effective Conservation.